

Deformation and Stress of Antenna Made of Glass Fiber Reinforced Plastics under Wind Force

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ABSTRACT

An investigation was conducted to determine the feasibility of glass fiber reinforced plastic antenna for meeting the mechanical design and wind resistance requirements of large antenna for application in telecommunication equipment. The investigation was carried out on the wind resistance of a GFRP antenna with a diameter of 1.8 m both theoretically and experimentally. The results obtained from this study show promise that glass fiber reinforced plastics can be used to light-weight, high-quality, large antennas for telecommunications with good structural integrity. The antenna tested successfully demonstrated its ability to meet requirements in typhoon.

INTRODUCTION

Recent developments in the full-scale production and evaluation of glass fiber reinforced plastics have demonstrated reasonably well the engineering importance of these high performance composite materials (1)~(3). Despite the fact that favorable combinations of strength, modulus, and density have been achieved on a production basis, it is generally conceded that the full potential of these productions has not yet been reached. This situation inevitably requests various evaluations for the full-scale production under a wide range of operating conditions. Since an antenna for telecommunications is usually installed on the top of buildings and/or towers, the antennas are subjected to a various kinds of severe external forces such as wind forces due to typhoon and large acceleration due to earthquake. If the antennas are made of glass fiber reinforced plastics and the utmost in reliability and efficient performance are required, it becomes necessary to calculate stresses and deformations due to wind forces and earthquake, and then to evaluate their reliability against these external forces in conjunction with the mechanical properties of materials.

In this study, experimental and theoretical investigations were carried out on a parabolic antenna made of glass fiber reinforced plastics (GFRP antenna) to evaluate the reliability for wind resistance requirements. Prior to this investigation, the baseline design of a GFRP antenna was performed. Based on the results of the evaluation of the preliminary designs, the configurations with light-weight, high-quality were selected for detail analysis evaluation. This was accomplished using finite element analysis. An experimental study was also

made on the GFRP antenna with a diameter of 1.8 m. Uniformly distributed load simulating to wind pressure was applied to the GFRP antenna using the test equipment so that the compressed air was supplied to an air bag. The stresses and deformations were measured by strain gauges and dial gauges. On the bases of those results, the magnitudes of stresses and deformations of the GFRP antenna under typhoon were estimated and then wind resistance characteristics were evaluated in comparison with the mechanical properties of composite material. Some discussions were also made on the feasibility of GFRP antennas for meeting the mechanical design.

BASELINE ANTENNA DESIGN

Design Concept

The dimensions of an antenna were determined on the bases of the calculated result using the finite element method. The design conditions selected for the GFRP antenna are those used for the mechanical design of aluminium antennas. Baseline design of the GFRP antenna was performed as first phase. In this baseline design, several observations may be performed on the calculated results: that is, the weight benefits of the antenna design compared to an all aluminium antenna can be substantial. A weight reduction of 30% is attained in this GFRP antenna. The amplitude of vibration of the GFRP antenna is greatly reduced relative to the all-aluminium antenna. The antenna including structures connecting to a tower has the requirement that the lowest natural frequency is beyond 30 Hz from the viewpoint of earthquake resistance. To meet this frequency request, the configurations of the GFRP antenna could be changed to move the lowest natural frequency up to about 45 Hz. The maximum stress values are compared with the allowable stresses. All the calculated stresses are fairly low within the design allowables. Under typhoon with a wind velocity of 60 m/s, however, much deformation than the design allowables will be expected. Consequently, considerable margin on the deformation is desirable at evaluation of the preliminary design phase. Based on the results of the evaluation of the preliminary designs, the configurations with light-weight, high-quality were selected for detail analysis evaluation.

Tested Antenna

The schematic view of the antenna is shown in Fig. 1. The antenna has a diameter of 1.8 m. The antenna can be divided into two parts: a reflector and a backstructure. Their thicknesses are 5 mm for the reflector and 6 mm for the backstructure. These two parts were fabricated separately and then bonded each other at the contacting portions in which glass fiber plies were covered. Semi-cured glass fiber plies impregnated with epoxy resin were performed to the specified shapes. These plies were stacked in a mold and hot-pressed under specified pressures and temperatures compatible with the resin and the adhesive systems.

Fig. 1 Schematic view of tested antenna

The manufacturing process developed during this program demonstrated that several prototype antennas could be manufactured with good uniformity and dimensional control, and that the process is capable of being scale up for production quantities of antennas.

In parallel with the baseline antenna design, a series of tests were carried out selecting composite materials for the GFRP antenna. These tests were consisted of environmental tests, tensile and bending tests. The environmental tests were carried out on six kinds of glass reinforced composites impregnated with epoxy resin. After these environmental tests, tensile and bending tests were carried out on those composites and then their tensile and bending strength,

modulie of elasticity were examined. Comparing these mechanical properties each other, the most suitable material was selected as the material for the GFRP antenna.

TEST EQUIPMENT AND TEST PROCEDURE

Experimental Setup

The schematic diagram of the test equipment is shown in Fig. 2. Allover view of the test equipment is shown in Fig. 3. As can be seen in Figs. 2 and 3, four holders were placed on a surface plate spacing 90 deg apart on the circumference with a distance of 425 mm from the center. The antenna was installed on the holders and then bolted.

Fig. 2 Schematic diagram of test equipment

Fig. 3 Allover view of test equipment

Since very precise loads might be applied if data for comparison with theory are generated, it was decided to use uniformly distributed load in order to simulate wind force acting on the antenna. After much study on the application of uniformly distributed load, it was thought out that a pressurized system using an air bag could be used in this test. This was accomplished by using the air bag, poles, and a cover bracket. Sixteen poles with screw at each top end were stood on end around the antenna. The air bag was inserted into an indentation of the antenna. The antenna was then covered with a cover bracket which was bolted to the poles.

Strain-gauge Measurements

Figs. 4 (a) and (b) show electrical-resistance strain gauges bonded on exterior and interior surfaces of the antenna. The strain gauges that were used in the instrumentation were KFC-5-D17-23 electrical-resistance strain gauges.

Fig. 4 Location diagram of strain gauge arrangement

The gauges were placed on both the exterior and interior surfaces of the reflector. The instrumentation was concentrated in one octant of the reflector. Three-element rosettes were installed on the planes of symmetry through the plane with an angle of 22.5 deg from the backplate center. Additional gauges were placed in the vicinity of one backplate at points where the highest local bending effects were expected.

Deflection Measurements

Dial-gauges, having a least count (value of smallest division) of 0.005 mm were used for deflection measurements in this test. A jig was designed and fabricated for mounting the dial-gauges. The jig was placed on the surface plate and the dial-gauges were mounted on them on the backside of the antenna. Fig. 5 shows the location diagram of the dial-gauge arrangement in the test set-up. Several deflection readings were taken at the maximum allowable load and at zero loads, and these deflection readings were averaged to obtain the reported deflection.

Fig. 5 Location diagram of dial-gauge arrangement

Test Procedure

As can be seen in Fig. 2, the compressed air was supplied to the air bag inserted in the indentation of the reflector and then uniformly distributed pressure was applied to the reflector. The test procedure consisted of first taking strain gauge readings and dial gauge readings at zero pressure and measuring strains and deflections at four equally spaced pressure levels which were 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, and 2.0 N/cm². Immediately after the completion of these tests, another set of readings at zero pressure was taken. This test procedure was repeated ten times. Data were accepted as reliable measures of strain and deflection if the final readings at zero pressure agreed within a strain of 10 x 10⁻⁶ and a deflection of 0.05 mm with the initial zero readings, and the indicator readings for four pressure levels and zero readings are plotted linearly with pressure.

There are several other important points that should be emphasized; that is, the automatic data taking-equipment with the constant current-time feature is required to reduce the effect of heating in the strain measurements. The precise time schedule must be observed-waiting for 1 min after applying the load before taking readings. This allows for compensation of any viscoelastic effects and time-delay load effects. Moreover, the use of multiple runs at any load increment was used to show reproducibility of the data. A separate computer sheet was generated that indicated the consistency of the test data. This was done by computing the standard deviation at each strain-gauge and dial-gauge location for all loads.

ANALYTICAL METHOD

Due to geometrical complexity and the generality of configuration, the finite-element method was chosen as the most suitable analytical technique (4)~(5). Recent experience using several general-purpose FEM computer programs and modeling techniques indicates that excellent correlation with experimental data from prototype testing is possible. The most efficient of these techniques has been an axisymmetrical modeling approach. This assumes the antenna to be symmetrical about its rotational centerline and hence requires that only an octant cross-section is modeled.

The finite-element analysis in this study was performed using a newly developed interactive, graphics-oriented package. It consists of a set of modular programs in which each program implements a specific task in the overall

numerical-analysis package. The use of modular programs is intended to encourage experimentation. For example, changes in boundary conditions, material properties, geometry, or other parameters can be quickly made in the specific program which stores them for use by other programs. Similarly, output files can be combined to study the effects of linear superposition on the resultant stress field. These features were utilized extensively in this study.

Figs. 6 (a) and (b) show finite element idealizations for an octant of the antenna. Fig. 6 (a) is the idealization for the cross section of the antenna, and Fig. 6 (b) is the plane figure of the idealization for the antenna. As shown in Fig. 6 (a), in this paper, the radial direction is defined as r direction, θ direction for the circumferential direction, and z direction for the vertical direction. The antenna was subdivided into a number of quadrilateral elements which were defined by the corner nodal point shown in Fig. 6 (b). To improve accuracy, smaller elements were used in zone where rapid variations in stress were anticipated.

Fig. 6 Finite element idealization for octant of antenna

Although the connecting portion between the reflector and the back structure was attached each other by fiber glass flies, the effect on the rigidity of the antenna is neglected because the bonded area is comparatively small. Accordingly, in this analysis, an assumption was made that the thickness of the connecting portion was the same as that of the reflector. As the antenna was installed on towers by the ball joints, no moment might act on the back-plate. The model points on the backplate should have no deformation because the backplate was a rigid body.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Relationship between Pressure and Deflection or Stress

Fig. 7 shows typical examples of the pressure-deflection and pressure-strain relations. In this figure, an indication of the individual results for a strain-gauge and dial-gauge, throughout the complete sequence up to full test pressure, is given as an example.

As can be seen in Fig. 7, all strain-gauges and dial-gauges generally indicated a linear behaviour with negligible hysteresis. Although the antenna was loaded up to full test pressure ten times repeatedly, the pressure-deflection and pressure-strain relations approximately coincided

Fig. 7 Relationship between pressure and strain or displacement

with each other for every loadings. This result means that preloading appeared to have no effect on the quantity of the results, in either linearity or hysteresis. These considerations indicate that there is no influence of loading and supporting figures in this test equipment, and that accurated measurements are taken of surface strains and deflections.

Comparison of Theoretical Results and Test Results

Pressure-Deflection Relation. Fig. 8 shows the comparison between the theoretical results and the test results of the deflection. All the data obtained have not been shown, but the data presented are representative samplings for $\theta = 0$ and 45 deg. As can be seen in Fig. 8, all the deflections measured are approximately in good agreement with the theoretical results.

Considering the deviation between the measured and calculated deflections in more detail, the measured deflections are about 30 percent higher than that of the calculated values in the vicinity of the backplate. This may be due to the effect of the frictional force acting on the ball joints. In this calculation, the boundary condition at the backplate portion was considered as thoroughly free. In actual antenna, however, a certain frictional force acts on the ball joints, leading to somewhat bending moment subjected to the backplate.

Fig. 8 Comparison between theoretical result and experimental result at pressure of 2.0 N/cm²

Strain Distribution. Fig. 9 shows the comparison between the numerical results and the test results of the stress produced on the interior surface of the reflector. Fig. 10 shows the one for the exterior surface of the reflector. In these figures, the maximum principal stresses obtained from the numerical calculation are plotted with the cross marks shown with the fine line in comparison with the ones obtained from the test, which are plotted with the cross marks shown with the bold-faced solid lines.

Fig. 9 Comparison between theoretical result and experimental result of stress produced on interior surface at pressure of 2.0 N/cm²

Fig. 10 Comparison between theoretical result and experimental result of stress produced on exterior surface at pressure of 2.0 N/cm²

It is noticed from these figures that the theoretical results are comparatively in good agreement with the test results. The satisfactory measure of agreement between theory and experiment indicates that the investigation contributes to a more logical approach to minimum weight design. However, of concern,

is the poor qualitative agreement in the stress value in the region of the backplate and in the vicinity of the outer periphery of the reflector. This may be caused by frictional forces acting on the ball joints. In addition, sufficient distributed load may not apply to the region of the outer periphery of the reflector because of loading fixture using air bag. However, the disagreements in stress magnitudes of theory and experiment are magnified because of the small absolute magnitude of the stress values. As a result, improved confidence has been obtained in design predictions from finite-element method which utilizes these experimental data.

Evaluation of Wind Resistance

As mentioned above, most of antennas for telecommunications are usually installed on the top of towers or buildings. Although in mechanical design these antenna configurations meet a lot of requirements necessary to demonstrate the design concept against various external existing forces such as wind pressure and earthquake, the wind resistance characteristic of antennas is a vitally important factor in design conditions in Japan, because typhoon may attack antennas every year.

The design conditions selected for the GFRP antennas are those used for the mechanical design of the aluminium antenna. The specific design condition for wind force is steady state operation at a wind velocity of 60 m/s. Wind pressure (6) is expressed by

$$p = \frac{1}{2} C_p \rho v^2 \quad (1)$$

where C_p = overall drag coefficient
 ρ = absolute density per unit volume
 v = wind velocity

Substituting $\rho = 1.25 \text{ N} \cdot \text{S}^2/\text{m}^4$ at room temperature and $v = 60 \text{ m/s}$ into Eq. (1), the following equation is obtained.

$$q = 2.25 \times 10^{-1} C_p \quad (\text{N/cm}^2) \quad (2)$$

In accordance with reference (6), the all-over drag coefficient for antenna with parabolic shape varies from 0.70 at the circumferential periphery to 1.53 at the center of the antenna. Substituting these values into Eq. (2), the wind pressure is then

$$p = (1.58 \text{ to } 3.34) \times 10^{-1} \quad (\text{N/cm}^2) \quad (3)$$

It is noticed from this value that the maximum pressure of 2.0 N/cm^2 selected in this test corresponds to about 6 times actual wind pressure.

Dividing the measured and calculated stresses by 6, therefore, the maximum principal stress becomes 1.9 to 2.0 N/mm^2 at the corner portion of the backplate. This result means that the GFRP antenna has enough strength to withstand external existing force caused by the wind with a velocity of 60 m/s. Similarly, dividing the measured and calculated displacements by 6, the maximum displacement becomes 0.23 mm at the outer periphery of the reflector. It is noticed from this result that the GFRP antenna has efficient stiffness required not to interfere with telecommunications under typhoon with a wind velocity of 60 m/s. The results obtained show promise that the GFRP composites can be used to make light-weight, high-quality, large antennas with good structural integrity.

CONCLUSIONS

An investigation was conducted to determine the feasibility of glass fiber reinforced composite antennas for meeting the mechanical design and wind resistance requirements of large antennas for telecommunications. The investigation was both theoretically and experimentally. The results obtained from this study are as follows:

- (1) The manufacturing process developed during this program demonstrated that

several prototype GFRP antennas could be manufactured with good uniformity and dimensional control and that the process is capable of being scale up for production quantities of antennas.

(2) An experimental method has been developed whereby uniformly distributed load simulating to wind force can be applied satisfactory to the GFRP antenna and accurate measurements are taken of surface strains.

(3) The stresses induced in the GFRP antenna are very small in comparison with the strength of the composite material provided in this study. This result suggests that in the design concept of GFRP antenna, evaluation of stiffness is more important factor than that of strength.

(4) The GFRP composites can be used to make light-weight, high-quality, large antennas with good structural integrity. The antennas tested successfully demonstrates their ability to meet steady-state operating conditions under external existing wind force.

(5) The comparison of the experimental results is comparatively in good agreement with the theoretical results obtained by finite element analysis. However, the poor qualitative agreement is found in the stress and deflection magnitudes in the region of the backplate and in the vicinity of the outer periphery of the reflector. This disagreement could be improved by obtaining the amount of constraint and the mesh concentration by comparison of the theoretical results with the experimental results.

(6) The combined use of numerical and experimental methods provides more information about the part being analyzed than does either method taken alone. When applied in this sense, a high user-oriented numerical-analysis package can be an ally rather than a rival to the efforts of the experienced experimental analyst.

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